

Breast CAncer STRatification project (B-CAST) gene panel

**THIS DOCUMENT IS INTENDED AS SUPPORTING MATERIAL FOR PUBLICATIONS
RELATED TO THE B-CAST GENE PANEL**

B-CAST gene panel development team §

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Abstract

As part of the Breast CAncer STRatification (B-CAST) project, we developed a gene panel composed of 323 genes that are frequently mutated in breast cancer and its molecular subtypes. The gene panel was constructed by combining results from a pooled analysis of individual patient data from 11 large-scale breast cancer sequencing studies and manual selection of genes with known associations with breast cancer. Here, we provide details on the construction of the B-CAST gene panel.

Background

The Breast CAncer STRatification project (B-CAST) is an international multicentered collaboration that aims to identify the genetic determinants of breast cancer molecular

subtypes. One of the objectives of the B-CAST project is to describe the association between somatic mutations and the etiology of breast cancer molecular subtypes. To do so, we developed a gene panel of frequently mutated genes in breast cancer that was used to sequence a large collection of breast tumors.

Pooled analysis of mutation datasets

The B-CAST gene panel was constructed to include the most frequently mutated genes in breast cancer. To select these genes, we first analyzed pooled patient-level mutation data from 11 breast cancer studies. The selected studies included both whole-genome and whole-exome breast cancer datasets (Banerji et al., 2012; Eirew et al., 2015; Ellis et al., 2012; Kim et al., 2015; Lim et al., 2014; Martelotto et al., 2015; Shah et al., 2012; Stephens et al., 2012; The Cancer Genome Atlas Network, 2012; Vaca-Paniagua et al., 2015; Yates et al., 2015). We homogenized the data to the human genome reference version 19 (hg19 / GRCh37) and annotated mutations using ANNOVAR (Wang et al., 2010). Combining the studies, we obtained a pooled dataset of 1,405 breast cancer samples, which we used to perform the gene selection.

Using the pooled mutation dataset, we prioritized genes using multiple criteria. We used MutSigCV (Lawrence et al., 2013) to identify significantly mutated genes (false discovery rate lower than 0.1) while correcting for gene size, transcriptional activity, open/closed chromatin state and DNA replication timing. We repeated this analysis for each individual breast cancer molecular subtype (luminal A, luminal B, Basal-like and HER2-enriched). We also selected genes that were described as driver genes (oncogenes or tumor suppressor genes) in the COSMIC (Forbes et al., 2008; Tate et al., 2018) or TSGene databases (Zhao et al., 2013) provided they were frequently mutated (>2% of the samples) in our pooled mutation dataset. The gene selection was complemented by including genes with a mutational frequency over 1% in our pooled mutation dataset that were also included in a similar gene panel (Griffith et al., 2018), whole-genome analysis (Nik-Zainal et al., 2012) or previous meta-analysis (Berger et al., 2018). To avoid the inclusion of genes that are not involved in cancer, we filtered out all non-cancer related genes using the gene damage index (Itan et al., 2015).

Manual inclusion of genes

As a complement to the pooled analysis, we manually included genes with a known or suspected role in breast cancer. We included candidate driver genes that were identified in a previous breast cancer sequencing study using Vogelstein's ratiometric method (Pereira et al., 2016; Vogelstein et al., 2013). We extended the gene selection by including likely target genes of breast cancer risk variants predicted using the INQUISIT pipeline (Michailidou et al., 2017). We included ERBB3, ERBB4, ESR1, FOXA1, and DNA damage repair genes, especially those involved in homologous recombination (i.e., BARD1, BRCA1, BRCA2, BRIP1, CHEK1, CHEK2, FAM175A, MRE11, NBN, PALB2, RAD51C and RAD51D), because of the high penetrance in breast cancer. We also included any additional gene that was available in the catalog of breast cancer driver genes from the International Cancer Genome Consortium pan-cancer analysis (Rheinbay et al., 2020). Finally, we added 10 additional genes from the BRIDGES panel that were not yet included (Breast Cancer Association Consortium et al., 2021). The BRIDGES panel includes 34 putative breast cancer susceptibility genes, nine of which were found to be strongly associated with increased breast cancer risk.

Additional genomic regions

Since the majority of the individuals sequenced in the B-CAST project were previously genotyped using the iCOGS (Bahcall, 2013) or OncoArray (Amos et al., 2017) genotyping arrays, we included 262 common SNPs to detect possible swaps during sample handling and to confirm sample identity. Finally, to enable estimating somatic copy number profiles, we included the 1,042 SNP probes scattered across the genome that were added to the MSK-IMPACT panel for that purpose (Cheng et al., 2015).

B-CAST gene panel

In summary, by combining a pooled analysis of mutation data with a manual inclusion of breast cancer-related genes we obtained a gene panel that targets ~1.6 Mb of the genome. This B-CAST gene panel comprises 323 genes that are frequently mutated in breast cancer and breast cancer subtypes (Table 1).

Table 1. The complete list of genes that were included in the B-CAST gene panel.

HUGO Gene Symbol	Ensembl Gene ID	Entrez Gene ID
ACVR1B	ENSG00000135503	91
ACVR2A	ENSG00000121989	92
ADCY3	ENSG00000138031	109
AGMO	ENSG00000187546	392636
AGTR2	ENSG00000180772	186
AKAP9	ENSG00000127914	10142
AKT1	ENSG00000142208	207
AKT2	ENSG00000105221	208
ALS2CR12	ENSG00000155749	130540
AP1S1	ENSG00000106367	1174
APC	ENSG00000134982	324
APITD1	ENSG00000175279	378708
APOBEC3A	ENSG00000128383	200315
APOBEC3B	ENSG00000179750	9582
ARHGAP35	ENSG00000160007	2909
ARHGEF6	ENSG00000129675	9459
ARID1A	ENSG00000117713	8289
ARID1B	ENSG00000049618	57492
ARID2	ENSG00000189079	196528
ARID5B	ENSG00000150347	84159
ARNTL	ENSG00000133794	406
ARRDC3	ENSG00000113369	57561
ASXL1	ENSG00000171456	171023
ATG10	ENSG00000152348	83734
ATM	ENSG00000149311	472
ATP6AP1L	ENSG00000205464	92270
ATR	ENSG00000175054	545
ATRX	ENSG00000085224	546
AXIN1	ENSG00000103126	8312
B2M	ENSG00000166710	567
BAP1	ENSG00000163930	8314

BARD1	ENSG00000138376	580
BAX	ENSG00000087088	581
BCOR	ENSG00000183337	54880
BCORL1	ENSG00000085185	63035
BIRC6	ENSG00000115760	57448
BLM	ENSG00000197299	641
BRAF	ENSG00000157764	673
BRCA1	ENSG00000012048	672
BRCA2	ENSG00000139618	675
BRD4	ENSG00000141867	23476
BRD7	ENSG00000166164	29117
BRIP1	ENSG00000136492	83990
BUB1B	ENSG00000156970	701
C16orf87	ENSG00000155330	388272
CACNA2D3	ENSG00000157445	55799
CASP8	ENSG00000064012	841
CBFB	ENSG00000067955	865
CBLB	ENSG00000114423	868
CBLC	ENSG00000142273	23624
CCAR1	ENSG00000060339	55749
CCND1	ENSG00000110092	595
CCND3	ENSG00000112576	896
CCNE1	ENSG00000105173	898
CD3G	ENSG00000160654	917
CDC27	ENSG00000004897	996
CDH1	ENSG00000039068	999
CDK12	ENSG00000167258	51755
CDK4	ENSG00000135446	1019
CDK6	ENSG00000105810	1021
CDKN1B	ENSG00000111276	1027
CDKN2A	ENSG00000147889	1029
CDKN2B	ENSG00000147883	1030
CHD4	ENSG00000111642	1108
CHD6	ENSG00000124177	84181
CHD8	ENSG00000100888	57680

CHEK1	ENSG00000149554	1111
CHEK2	ENSG00000183765	11200
CIC	ENSG00000079432	23152
CNOT3	ENSG00000088038	4849
COL11A1	ENSG00000060718	1301
COX11	ENSG00000166260	1353
CREBBP	ENSG00000005339	1387
CSMD1	ENSG00000183117	64478
CTCF	ENSG00000102974	10664
CTNNA1	ENSG00000044115	1495
CTNNA3	ENSG00000183230	29119
CTNNB1	ENSG00000168036	1499
CUL1	ENSG00000055130	8454
CUL3	ENSG00000036257	8452
CUL5	ENSG00000166266	8065
CUX1	ENSG00000257923	1523
CYLD	ENSG00000083799	1540
DCC	ENSG00000187323	1630
DCLRE1B	ENSG00000118655	64858
DDA1	ENSG00000130311	79016
DDX3X	ENSG00000215301	1654
DEPDC1B	ENSG00000035499	55789
DIS3	ENSG00000083520	22894
DLC1	ENSG00000164741	10395
DNMT3A	ENSG00000119772	1788
DYNLRB2	ENSG00000168589	83657
ECT2L	ENSG00000203734	345930
EEF1A1	ENSG00000156508	1915
EGFR	ENSG00000146648	1956
ELAC2	ENSG00000006744	60528
ELK4	ENSG00000158711	2005
EP300	ENSG00000100393	2033
ERBB2	ENSG00000141736	2064
ERBB2IP	ENSG00000112851	55914
ERBB3	ENSG00000065361	2065

ERBB4	ENSG00000178568	2066
ERCC4	ENSG00000175595	2072
ERCC5	ENSG00000134899	2073
ESR1	ENSG00000091831	2099
EXO1	ENSG00000174371	9156
EZH2	ENSG00000106462	2146
FAF1	ENSG00000185104	11124
FAIM3	ENSG00000162894	9214
FAM175A	ENSG00000163322	84142
FAN1	ENSG00000198690	22909
FANCC	ENSG00000158169	2176
FANCM	ENSG00000187790	57697
FAS	ENSG00000026103	355
FAT1	ENSG00000083857	2195
FBXW7	ENSG00000109670	55294
FGFR2	ENSG00000066468	2263
FGFR4	ENSG00000160867	2264
FIBP	ENSG00000172500	9158
FLT4	ENSG00000037280	2324
FOXA1	ENSG00000129514	3169
FOXO3	ENSG00000118689	2309
FOXP1	ENSG00000114861	27086
FOXQ1	ENSG00000164379	94234
FRG1	ENSG00000109536	2483
FRS2	ENSG00000166225	10818
GATA3	ENSG00000107485	2625
GATA6	ENSG00000141448	2627
GATAD2A	ENSG00000167491	54815
GEN1	ENSG00000178295	348654
GNA13	ENSG00000120063	10672
GNAS	ENSG00000087460	2778
GNG2	ENSG00000186469	54331
GPS2	ENSG00000132522	2874
GPSM2	ENSG00000121957	29899
GXYLT1	ENSG00000151233	283464

HAPLN4	ENSG00000187664	404037
HCFC2	ENSG00000111727	29915
HELQ	ENSG00000163312	113510
HFM1	ENSG00000162669	164045
HIST1H3B	ENSG00000124693	8358
HIST1H3D	ENSG00000197409	8351
HLA-DRB1	ENSG00000196126	3123
HMGCLL1	ENSG00000146151	54511
HNRNPD	ENSG00000138668	3184
HRAS	ENSG00000174775	3265
HSPA4	ENSG00000170606	3308
IDH1	ENSG00000138413	3417
IGF1R	ENSG00000140443	3480
IGF2	ENSG00000167244	3481
INSRR	ENSG00000027644	3645
IRS4	ENSG00000133124	8471
JAK1	ENSG00000162434	3716
KANSL1	ENSG00000120071	284058
KDM5C	ENSG00000126012	8242
KDM6A	ENSG00000147050	7403
KEAP1	ENSG00000079999	9817
KMT2A	ENSG00000118058	4297
KMT2C	ENSG00000055609	58508
KMT2D	ENSG00000167548	8085
KRAS	ENSG00000133703	3845
L3MBTL3	ENSG00000198945	84456
LARP7	ENSG00000174720	51574
LATS1	ENSG00000131023	9113
LIG4	ENSG00000174405	3981
MAP2K4	ENSG00000065559	6416
MAP3K1	ENSG00000095015	4214
MAP3K13	ENSG00000073803	9175
MAP3K4	ENSG00000085511	4216
MAU2	ENSG00000129933	23383
MCC	ENSG00000171444	4163

MCL1	ENSG00000143384	4170
MDM2	ENSG00000135679	4193
MECOM	ENSG00000085276	2122
MED12	ENSG00000184634	9968
MED23	ENSG00000112282	9439
MEN1	ENSG00000133895	4221
MET	ENSG00000105976	4233
MLH1	ENSG00000076242	4292
MLLT4	ENSG00000130396	4301
MNAT1	ENSG00000020426	4331
MORC4	ENSG00000133131	79710
MRE11A	ENSG00000020922	4361
MSH2	ENSG00000095002	4436
MSH3	ENSG00000113318	4437
MSH4	ENSG00000057468	4438
MSR1	ENSG00000038945	4481
MTOR	ENSG00000198793	2475
MUC16	ENSG00000181143	94025
MUTYH	ENSG00000132781	4595
MYB	ENSG00000118513	4602
MYC	ENSG00000136997	4609
MYH10	ENSG00000133026	4628
MYH9	ENSG00000100345	4627
NBN	ENSG00000104320	4683
NCOR1	ENSG00000141027	9611
NEIL1	ENSG00000140398	79661
NEIL2	ENSG00000154328	252969
NEK10	ENSG00000163491	152110
NF1	ENSG00000196712	4763
NF2	ENSG00000186575	4771
NIPBL	ENSG00000164190	25836
NOTCH1	ENSG00000148400	4851
NOTCH2	ENSG00000134250	4853
NRAS	ENSG00000213281	4893
NSD1	ENSG00000165671	64324

NTN4	ENSG00000074527	59277
NUDT17	ENSG00000186364	200035
NUP93	ENSG00000102900	9688
OPCML	ENSG00000183715	4978
PALB2	ENSG00000083093	79728
PARK2	ENSG00000185345	5071
PARP3	ENSG00000041880	10039
PARP4	ENSG00000102699	143
PBRM1	ENSG00000163939	55193
PDGFRA	ENSG00000134853	5156
PDGFRL	ENSG00000104213	5157
PFKFB3	ENSG00000170525	5209
PHF6	ENSG00000156531	84295
PHOX2B	ENSG00000109132	8929
PIK3CA	ENSG00000121879	5290
PIK3R1	ENSG00000145675	5295
PIK3R3	ENSG00000117461	8503
PMS1	ENSG00000064933	5378
PMS2	ENSG00000122512	5395
POLI	ENSG00000101751	11201
POLN	ENSG00000130997	353497
POLR2C	ENSG00000102978	5432
POLR2F	ENSG00000100142	5435
PPM1D	ENSG00000170836	8493
PPP2R1A	ENSG00000105568	5518
PPP2R4	ENSG00000119383	5524
PPP4R4	ENSG00000119698	57718
PPP6R2	ENSG00000100239	9701
PRC1	ENSG00000198901	9055
PRDM1	ENSG00000057657	639
PREX2	ENSG00000046889	80243
PRKCI	ENSG00000163558	5584
PRR16	ENSG00000184838	51334
PRRG1	ENSG00000130962	5638
PTEN	ENSG00000171862	5728

PTPRD	ENSG00000153707	5789
PVRL4	ENSG00000143217	81607
RAD23B	ENSG00000119318	5887
RAD50	ENSG00000113522	10111
RAD51B	ENSG00000182185	5890
RAD51C	ENSG00000108384	5889
RAD51D	ENSG00000185379	5892
RASA1	ENSG00000145715	5921
RASA2	ENSG00000155903	5922
RB1	ENSG00000139687	5925
RB1CC1	ENSG00000023287	9821
RCCD1	ENSG00000166965	91433
RCN1	ENSG00000049449	5954
RDM1	ENSG00000187456	201299
RECQL	ENSG00000004700	5965
RELN	ENSG00000189056	5649
RFC1	ENSG00000035928	5981
RFC3	ENSG00000133119	5983
RHOA	ENSG00000067560	387
RINT1	ENSG00000135249	60561
RNF213	ENSG00000173821	57674
RNF43	ENSG00000108375	54894
RPL22	ENSG00000116251	6146
RPL5	ENSG00000122406	6125
RPS23	ENSG00000186468	6228
RUNX1	ENSG00000159216	861
SARM1	ENSG00000004139	23098
SDHA	ENSG00000073578	6389
SEC24D	ENSG00000150961	9871
SEPT9	ENSG00000184640	10801
SETD2	ENSG00000181555	29072
SETDB1	ENSG00000143379	9869
SF3B1	ENSG00000115524	23451
SH3GL1	ENSG00000141985	6455
SLC22A18	ENSG00000110628	5002

SLC26A3	ENSG00000091138	1811
SLC4A7	ENSG00000033867	9497
SMAD4	ENSG00000141646	4089
SMARCA4	ENSG00000127616	6597
SMARCC1	ENSG00000173473	6599
SMC6	ENSG00000163029	79677
SMG1	ENSG00000157106	23049
SOX2	ENSG00000181449	6657
SOX4	ENSG00000124766	6659
SOX9	ENSG00000125398	6662
SPATA3	ENSG00000173699	130560
SPEN	ENSG00000065526	23013
SPOP	ENSG00000121067	8405
SSBP4	ENSG00000130511	170463
STAG2	ENSG00000101972	10735
STAT6	ENSG00000166888	6778
STK11	ENSG00000118046	6794
STXBP4	ENSG00000166263	252983
SYNCRIP	ENSG00000135316	10492
TAF1	ENSG00000147133	6872
TBL1XR1	ENSG00000177565	79718
TBX3	ENSG00000135111	6926
TET2	ENSG00000168769	54790
TGFBR2	ENSG00000163513	7048
TJP1	ENSG00000104067	7082
TMEM184B	ENSG00000198792	25829
TOB1	ENSG00000141232	10140
TOP3B	ENSG00000100038	8940
TP53	ENSG00000141510	7157
TRAF3	ENSG00000131323	7187
TRRAP	ENSG00000196367	8295
UBR5	ENSG00000104517	51366
URM1	ENSG00000167118	81605
USP9X	ENSG00000124486	8239
UVSSA	ENSG00000163945	57654

WAS	ENSG00000015285	7454
XBP1	ENSG00000100219	7494
XPO1	ENSG00000082898	7514
XRCC2	ENSG00000196584	7516
YWHAZ	ENSG00000164924	7534
ZC3H13	ENSG00000123200	23091
ZFHX3	ENSG00000140836	463
ZFP36L1	ENSG00000185650	677
ZFP36L2	ENSG00000152518	678
ZNF217	ENSG00000171940	7764
ZNF404	ENSG00000176222	342908
ZNF703	ENSG00000183779	80139

List of abbreviations

- B-CAST: Breast Cancer Stratification project.
- INQUISIT: Integrated Expression Quantitative Trait and *in silico* Prediction of GWAS Targets.
- COSMIC: Catalogue of Somatic Mutations in Cancer.
- TCGA: The Cancer Genome Atlas.
- BRIDGES: Breast Cancer Risk after Diagnostic Gene Sequencing.

Additional notes

Raw data, selection of genes, and definition of sequenced genomic coordinates were obtained as a collaboration between VIB-KU Center for Cancer Biology, Leuven, Belgium (VIB), the Netherlands Cancer Institute, Amsterdam, The Netherlands (NKI-AVL), University of Santiago de Compostela, Santiago de Compostela, Spain (USC) and The Center for Genomic Regulation and National Center of Genomic Analysis, Barcelona, Spain (CRG-CNAG).

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